

SOME RECOMMENDATION FOR KARAKALPAK LEARNERS' ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS.

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Abstract:

The thesis is aimed at providing methodological approaches to teach English for the learners whose native language is Karakalpak. It is naturally to have difference between English and Karakalpak language, as the former is Indo-European while the latter is Turkey language. Both of them have different Grammar and Lexical peculiarities. So this work tries to give effective tips for those phenomenons.

Introduction

Error correction a crucial aspect of foreign language teaching, but also one of the most complex decisions the teacher has to make in a foreign language classroom. However, based on the personal experiences of pre-service teachers and scientific findings, the first thing to do, even before deciding on the appropriate error correction technique, is to prepare the learners to receive corrective feedback and regard it as part of learning a foreign language. Having a positive attitude towards corrective feedback is the first step in making error correction a necessary part of language acquisition. Furthermore, it is crucial that the learners notice the teacher's correction following their error, because, according to the Noticing Hypothesis, it is only that part of the corrective feedback that is noticed by the learner that turns into intake, the internalised part of the input. Teachers should also take into consideration the fact that even error correction can and should be provided within a communicative context so that their learners will have as many opportunities to be involved in meaningful communication in the foreign language as possible. Apart from correcting learners' errors verbally, teachers have the choice of using nonverbal techniques of error correction, which are also unobtrusive in nature. They can use various gestures, facial expressions, pointing, and other metalinguistic cues that do not interfere with the communication flow and do not deprive the learners of valuable speaking time. Besides, such techniques can be humorous and contribute to a friendly atmosphere in the classroom. Another aspect of corrective feedback, which is perhaps neglected in the education of young teachers, is written error correction. As in verbal correction, teachers also have an abundance of techniques to choose from when correcting written compositions. What might be the most useful, however, is self-correction, which provides the learners with the opportunity to reflect more deeply on their errors and eventually learn more from them than if the correct solution is simply provided by the teacher. The teacher is there to give cues, and it is the learners' task to come to the correct form. This statement is in line with Vygotsky's sociocultural theory of language acquisition, which suggests that teachers should use scaffolding when providing corrective feedback. This means that they should give their learners the amount of help they need to correct their own errors and no more than needed. However, this is nearly impossible when working with young learners. Corrective feedback becomes a real challenge in the classroom of very young learners, due to their lack of metalinguistic knowledge, short attention span, and other factors. This is why teachers who work with this group of learners need to be even more patient and combine various types of feedback until they find methods which suit their learners best. Apart from age, there are a number of other individual factors, such as

the learners' intelligence, language aptitude, motivation, attitudes towards language learning, and proficiency, that teachers should take into account when choosing the appropriate method of error correction. Due to the individual differences among learners, which determine how they notice and perceive corrective feedback, one technique which has proved to be excellent for one group of learners may be completely useless in another group. All in all, the conclusion can be reached that there is no right way of correcting learners' errors. It is the teacher's task to find a method which both serves its purpose – providing a basis for further language acquisition – and is well accepted by their group of learners.

To conclude, from this study I discovered that students/learners' language errors are not static (fossilized) but dynamic. They can be disappeared through pedagogical language instructions. At a certain step of language learning, these errors appear. As a result of instructions, some errors stabilized. Other new types of errors are prone to appear when learners use new grammatical items. Grammatical errors maintain dynamic as the learners continue learning foreign languages. In this way, the learners' interlanguage system improves into target language structure. Furthermore, grammar instruction helps to destabilization of errors because it comprises grammar explanation, feedback and the learner given a chance to practice. The stabilized errors are more likely to fossilize if the learner stops learning the language or limit exposure of target language. Then errors become permanent characteristic of the learners' interlanguage system. In contrast, when learners continue learning target language, the process of destabilization also continues, interlanguage alters its state and finally can constitute part of the target language.

In addition, the learner has the ability to acquire language system: grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation.

Without knowing possible meaning and interpretations of syntactic stylistic constructions of the English and Karakalpak languages it is impossible for the teachers to give proper knowledge to the future philologists and teachers in teaching process.

Used literature

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